

DEVELOPMENT OF INNOVATION PROJECT MANAGEMENT SYSTEM IN ENTERPRISES

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Abstract: *Modern technologies and platforms have helped businesses and individuals to reduce costs by minimizing personal communication with customers, partners and government organizations, and also made it possible to communicate more quickly and easily.*

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In developed countries, this indicator makes up more than 70 percent of GDP and combines public administration, consulting and information services, finance, wholesale and retail trade, as well as services (utility, personal and social). The higher the diversification and dynamics of the economy, the greater the circulation of unique information inside and outside the country, and the greater the information traffic within national economies. Therefore, the digital economy develops rapidly in markets where the number of participants is large and IT services are widespread. In particular, it creates unlimited convenience for transport, trade, logistics and similar industries that actively work with the Internet.

What is the cost of our innovative project? The question is often raised when it comes to estimating whether a project can cover its costs. In some cases, production costs may already be affected and the need to determine the cost of the project may be due to changes in the terms of the purchase agreement or costs. In any case, the value of the project depends on the market conditions, the

implementation depending on the development of the work, as well as its prospects. This cost may change the decision to continue working on the project in the future, given the flexibility of the managers. For example, loss-averse managers may reject a project if it has a negative economic outlook, given the current state of the project and market conditions. If our assessment does not consider the possibility of using a realistic option, this can lead to an underestimation of the profitability of the project and the loss of investment opportunities to generate cost.

The most important feature of the method of real options is the ability to consider rapidly changing economic conditions, in which the subject is of particular importance in the current situation in the world economy. At the same time, as a rule, the method of cash flow discounting is based on the evaluation of any value of projects, despite the fact that this method has its own characteristics, and is not suitable for analysis in the conditions of the situation. uncertainty. The advantages of the income approach are its universality and theoretical foundation. This approach makes it possible to determine the price of assets (market, investments, etc.) depending on the type of operations performed and valuation tasks, as well as to consider future income, expectations and economic depreciation, taking into account the mechanism of economic depreciation.

The main disadvantage of the income approach is the complexity of obtaining the initial data necessary for labor costs and calculations. Applying this approach is very complicated because it is difficult to predict the future income that the party implementing the project will receive. Thus, information about future earnings is likely to be uncertain in nature. Disadvantages of the method of discounting cash flows may have an insignificant effect on the evaluation results, but the use of this method in the assessment of risk investment opportunities in connection with uncertainty and the need to make decisions often becomes a

source of errors. is already a characteristic of the project and determines its price. In practice, various modifications of this method are used. In particular, instead of taking into account the project risk in the discount rate, risk accounting for the valuation of the company corresponds to cash flows: the expected cash flows are "weighted" according to the inherent risks of the business. Thus, the specific risks of biotechnological companies are related to the passage of the stages of development of the biotechnological project to be implemented (the main stages in the development of pharmacological preparations (medicines) separate some stages of clinical trials).

Thus, the discount rate only takes into account the risks of projects that have passed all stages. The application of the income approach is most optimally expressed, since the value of the project consists in the ability to generate future cash flows. In addition, the importance is represented by the risks associated with these cash flows. If, as an addition to the method of discounting cash flows, the method of real options can be presented in general, a real option, as an opportunity to implement one or another action (in our case, the opportunity to implement innovation), a project that has legal or physical entities). This is an opportunity that others do not have and consequently has value: the opportunity to start producing the product (the real option) is reflected in the cost.

This opportunity can exceed the costs of this realization if there is a probability of receiving a total profit from the implementation of this possibility (if such a probability is zero, the real option will not have costs). The real options method allows you to determine the price of such options.

Many financial experts in the field of valuation, such as Tom Copeland and Aswath Damodaran, support the use of a multi-view approach to the valuation of a high-tech startup. Different venture entities (related to innovative projects) may or may not differ in the sequence of intermediate stages, so the assessment will

depend on the probability of approaching the next stage. This uncertainty, as a rule, leads to a more complex, multi-view analysis and greater creativity of the appraiser.

Also, when valuing a start-up, it may be important whether we use cash flow or net income, as large amounts of cash flow are lower in a start-up than in a mature company. Fortunately, the main thing that should guide investors when choosing valuation methods is the availability of information and the appropriate personnel who can competently use this information in order to make the most profitable investment of funds.

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